

Dynamic Fragmentation Patterns in Flexed Ceramic Discs

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Fragmentation arising from dynamic fracture of flexed ceramic discs is considered at three different length scales—the number of fragments generated, the mass distribution of the fragments, and the branching distance of propagating cracks. Indentation-strength techniques are used to control the strain energy at failure in polycrystalline ceramic specimens, thereby enabling clear measurements of fragmentation phenomena at all three scales. Data from these tests are combined with data determined from an extensive survey of published works, encompassing over forty glasses and ceramics, leading to quantitative comparisons of the parameters used to characterize fragmentation patterns. Assessments include suppression of the number of fragments generated on failure of ceramics relative to glasses, the substantial decrease in width of fragment mass distributions generated by disc flexure relative to explosively generated fragments, and the correlation of crack branching resistance with material fracture resistance. Innovative data presentation schemes are introduced to aid in these assessments. Examples of practical application of the data are included.

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1. Introduction

Fragmentation patterns often develop during brittle failure when crack velocities are extremely large and fracture is rapid. An example of a fragmentation pattern that developed in a glass-ceramic disc fractured in biaxial flexure is shown in Fig. 1(a). The pattern consists of two cracks that propagated in opposite directions from a strength controlling flaw at the disc center before a series of sequential crack branching events formed a radiating fragmentation pattern composed of fragments with angular points. The entire pattern developed in less than 100 μs with crack velocities greater than 1 km s^{-1} . Such crack velocities are comparable to the speed of bulk acoustic waves, leading to dynamic fracture conditions in which the kinetic energy of wave motion in the material is comparable to the mechanical and surface energies that control quasi-static fracture [Lawn, 1993]. The nature of fragmentation patterns formed by biaxial flexure of ceramic discs such as in Fig. 1(a) is the focus of the work here.

Figure 1. Optical images of three fragmentation patterns. (a) Glass ceramic disc fractured in biaxial flexure—the topic of this work. (b) Region of polymeric film fractured by thermal expansion mismatch with substrate. (c) Region of wet starch film fractured by desiccation.

Fragmentation of biaxially loaded discs into predominantly radial patterns was noted in the earliest brittle fracture studies. In considerations of “the propagation of fissures in glass ...”, Preston hypothesized that cracks propagate in brittle materials so as to maintain directions at right angles to the principal tension [Preston, 1931] and that the direction of this tension may change as the crack advances. In particular, if an instability splits the “wave-front” (forming what is now termed “hackle”) then the crack will fork or form “radiants” as the tension experienced by each crack front segment will be in a different direction. Preston noted that the tendency to forking increased with increasing glass strength [Preston, 1935]. Schematic diagrams of fragmentation patterns formed in glass under uniaxial or equibiaxial tension, identical to that shown in Fig. 1(a), were presented [Preston, 1931; 1935]. Preston also noted that the crack branching phenomenon produced “dagger-shaped fragments ... that makes glass dangerous” [Preston, 1935]. Clearly, the number, size, shape, and kinetic energy of fragments formed when a brittle material fractures determine the capacity for injury, and hence the original focus of the manufacturers of glass products for domestic use, and more recently for architectural and automotive applications, in minimizing the capacity for fragmentation or to contain the fragments once formed [Bennison *et al.*, 1999].

Images of fragmentation patterns similar to Fig. 1(a) and as described by Preston have been reported for biaxially stressed discs of many materials, but principally glass [Gorham, and Rickerby, 1975; Matthewson and Field, 1980; Shetty *et al.*, 1983a; Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1990; Quinn, 1999; Quinn *et al.*, 2005; Salem, 2013; DeLellis *et al.*, 2020]. In addition, Terao [1978] describes fragmentation patterns in glass similar to Fig. 1(a), generated by localized heating and consequent biaxial stress fields, from the extensive and very early, 1930s, work of Hirata. Images of fragmentation patterns similar to Fig. 1(a) formed in biaxially stressed discs of other materials include: ion exchanged glass [Donald and Hill, 1988; Hill and Donald, 1989; Donald *et al.*, 1993; Kooi *et al.*, 2008; Tandon and Glass, 2015]; polycrystalline alumina [Shetty *et al.*, 1983b; Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1990; Borger *et al.*, 2002]; porous alumina [Saposhnikov *et al.*, 2015]; polycrystalline MgF₂ [Mecholsky *et al.*, 1998, 2020]; polycrystalline Si₃N₄ [Quinn and Wirth, 1989, 1990]; polycrystalline ZrO₂ [Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1990, 1991]; acryl [Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1991]; single crystal and polycrystalline Si [Cook, 2006]; and polycrystalline spinel [Tokariev *et al.*, 2012; Salem, 2013]. Images of fracture in biaxially loaded square plates of glass-ceramic and alumina [Shetty *et al.*, 1981; Choi *et al.*, 2000] are similar to Fig. 1(a). Laser-induced cracks in single crystal Si discs [Murr and Szilva, 1975] are similar to those formed by localized heating studied by Hirata. Fragmentation patterns generated by uniaxial loading, also similar to those described by Preston, have been reported many times for glass rods and bars [Terao, 1953; Bowden *et al.*, 1967; Congleton and Petch, 1967; Blauel and Richter, 1969; Field, 1971; Sundaram and Tippur, 2018; Nakamura *et al.*, 2020] and appear as one half of the pattern

shown in Fig. 1(a). Mixed-mode loading, uniaxial + shear, such as occurs in pressurized glass bottles or tubes [Aoki and Sakata, 1980; Bradt, 2011; Quinn, 2020], or shear loading of glass lathes [Quinn, 2020] have also been observed to give rise to patterns similar to those of Fig. 1(a). Figure 2 shows an enlarged view of the central region of Fig. 1(a) at the length scale of primary crack branching. The strength-controlling flaw is located between the two initial cracks and subsequent crack bifurcation and trifurcation events leading to specimen-level fragmentation. Localized images of biaxially-loaded specimens, similar to Fig. 2, showing cracking at the length scale of initial branching have also been reported for Si_3N_4 and SiC [Choi and Gyekenyesi, 1998] and glass [Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1991; Tang *et al.*, 2014; Sundaram *et al.*, 2018]. Pervasive crack branching, Fig. 2, and consequent fragmentation pattern formation, Fig. 1(a), in brittle material fracture has become so well accepted that the phenomena are sometimes studied quantitatively with no accompanying image [Kirchner, 1978; Deobald and Kobayashi, 1992; Oakley, 1996].

Figure 2. Enlarged view of failure location of glass ceramic disc from Fig. 1(a), showing initial flaw location and crack branching events.

In examining images such as Fig. 1(a) or Fig. 2, care must be taken to recognize that fragmentation of brittle materials also occurs under the localized loading of sharp contacts or indentations or impacts. If the locally contacted or impacted material is in the form of a disc or plate, the resulting fragmentation patterns can often appear superficially similar to those generated by global biaxial loading. In both local and global loading fragmentation, there are predominant radiating “primary” cracks, as observed, for example, in impact experiments on Al_2O_3 [Jones *et al.*, 2017] and porcelain [Fragassa *et al.*, 2018]. However, contact or impact generated fragmentation patterns differ from biaxially generated patterns in that there are many closely separated primary cracks that rarely branch and many secondary circumferential

“secondary” cracks that form between the primary cracks. These observations are particularly common in tempered or exchanged glasses containing central zones of tension [Barstow and Edgerton, 1939; Hillig and Charles, 1961; Zijlstra and Burgraaf, 1969; Sakai *et al.*, 1991; Glass *et al.*, 2007; Kooi *et al.*, 2008; Lee *et al.*, 2012; Davydova and Uvarov, 2013; Tandon and Glass, 2015; Karlsson, 2017], but also observed in SiC [Zinszner *et al.*, 2012, 2015; Forquin *et al.*, 2018] and other materials, as noted in a review of impact by Subhash *et al.* [2008]. Fracture systems in other materials also form fragmentation patterns, as shown in Figs. 1(b) and (c). Thin films with elastic, plastic, or thermal expansion properties different from the substrate often exhibit fragmentation patterns if the substrate is mechanically loaded or the temperature of the system is altered. The patterns that develop in these cases frequently consist of arrays of long, parallel, primary cracks with shorter, secondary cracks spanning the primary cracks, so as to form “ladders.” In many cases the patterns resemble cracks generated in ion-exchanged glasses far from an impact or contact site. The pattern in Fig. 1(b) exhibits these features and was formed by cooling a polymeric film between two quartz plates. Other systems exhibiting similar patterns include metallic or oxide films on stretched polymeric substrates [Frank *et al.*, 2009; Wu *et al.*, 2015; Ruoho *et al.*, 2020]. Films formed of solid particles held together by a liquid often exhibit fragmentation patterns when the liquid evaporates. Such patterns are formed by desiccation cracks that often generate planar arrays of cells with convoluted edges, forming “mud-flat” patterns [Goehring *et al.*, 2015]. The pattern in Fig. 1(c) exhibits these features and was formed by drying a water saturated starch film on a glass substrate. Often such patterns form within larger fragments with straight-sides in both drying and stretching geometries [Gao *et al.*, 1998; Qin *et al.*, 2013; Seghir and Arscott, 2015]. It is clear that the desiccation cracks of Fig. 1(c) do not resemble those of Fig. 1(a), as noted earlier in experiments on alumina and agar powders [Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1994].

The work here is divided into three further major sections, each focussing on an experimental aspect of fragmentation of brittle materials, largely ceramics, in biaxial flexure. The sections proceed in order of decreasing length scale: First, the scale of the specimen (number of fragments), second, the scale of the fragment (mass distributions), and third, the scale of the crack (branching distances). Although each of these subjects has been considered before in various contexts they have not been linked or simultaneously considered in a single study. Here, original experimental results are presented in each of the three sections and combined with previously published results from other works where appropriate. Fragmentation patterns generated by impacts or contacts, thin film constraints, or desiccation are not considered.

2. Number of fragments

Results from a variety of polycrystalline ceramic materials were generated for this investigation and combined with results on amorphous (glassy), single crystalline, and polycrystalline materials published by other researchers and the current author. The polycrystalline materials examined here were AlN, Ca-doped Al₂O₃, Cr-doped Al₂O₃, cordierite (2MgO–2Al₂O₃–5SiO₂) glass-ceramic, MgO, and Y₂O₃. All samples except AlN were used in previously published ceramic strength studies [Cook, 1990, 1994ab, 2005, 2015]. A range of grain-sizes was included for the Ca-Al₂O₃ and MgO materials [Cook, 1990, 1994b], cubic phase and larger grain-sized mixed cubic + hexagonal phase materials were included for the Y₂O₃ materials [Cook 1994b], and base and compressive surface-stressed materials were included for the glass-ceramic [Cook, 2005]. The grain-size d , Young's modulus E , and fracture resistance R , of the materials is given in Table 1 along with the dimensions, diameter \times thickness, of the disc specimens used for strength testing. The AlN and Al₂O₃ materials were tested in their as-sintered form, the MgO was polished to the 6 μm level and then annealed, and the glass-ceramic and Y₂O₃ materials were polished to the 1 μm level. Full specimen details are given in the earlier works [Cook, 1990, 1994ab, 2005, 2015].

The testing consisted of a two-step procedure, here briefly outlined. First, the disc specimens were indented with a Vickers diamond pyramid in the center of the prospective tensile test face, using controlled peak contact loads, P , in the domain 0.2–300 N. The indentation contact generated a square plastic deformation impression and stable cracks emanating from the impression corners. The contact load determined the indentation crack size and thus controlled the dominant flaw size in a disc. **Figure 3** shows indentation flaws formed at two different indentation loads in the glass-ceramic material and demonstrates how the flaw size was controlled. As the flaw size determines the maximum sustainable stress or strength of the specimen, the strength σ and hence stored elastic strain energy in the specimen at failure, $\sim \sigma^2/E$, are easily controlled through the indentation load. Second, the specimens were broken in biaxial flexure using a flat-on-three-ball test jig [Marshall, 1980]. Most failure times were less than 50 ms, using a piezoelectric load cell to monitor the failure loads. Such times ensure “inert” conditions by not allowing diffusion of reactive species such as water to the crack tip during failure. Failure stresses were calculated from plate theory [Roark and Young, 1983] and the testing rig dimensions, diameters of three-ball circular support \times circular loading flat, given in Table 1. Stressing rates for these tests were approximately 10^4 MPa s^{-1} . In order to examine the effect of “reactive” conditions on the strength and subsequent fragmentation behavior, some tests on the glass ceramic were conducted in water at slower stressing rates extending to $10^{-2} \text{ MPa s}^{-1}$.

Figure 3. Optical micrographs of Vickers indentation flaws in cordierite glass ceramic at the indentation loads P indicated. The residual contact impression and crack lengths increase with load, enabling control of specimen strengths. A chip of material separated from the material is visible at the larger indentation load.

Figure 4 shows examples of strength behavior for the glass-ceramic. Base and surface-stressed specimen strengths [Cook, 2005] are indicated by the open and closed symbols, respectively. Solid lines are indentation fracture mechanics-based best fits to the data. Decreasing the indentation load increased the size of the failure-causing flaw and hence the inert strength decreased with increasing load, **Fig. 4(a)**. At very small loads the specimens failed from flaws intrinsic to the specimen, and “intrinsic strength” is indicated by the left bands. At large loads chipping led to strength increase above the ideal response. Similar indentation and intrinsic strength behavior were observed for the other materials. Glass-ceramic specimens containing a compressive surface stress exhibited greater strengths at a given indentation load than the base material. Decreasing the applied stressing rate in water provides more time for activated crack growth and hence the reactive strength decreased with decreasing stressing rate, **Fig. 4(b)**. At very fast stressing rates the reactive strengths approached the inert level, indicated by the right bands. Specimens with compressive surface stress exhibited greater strengths at a given stressing rate. Extensive details of indentation strength are given elsewhere [Cook, 2005, 2015].

Figure 4. Plots of indentation strength for cordierite glass-ceramic discs. (a) Inert strength, in which indentation load, and thus flaw size, is varied and stressing rate is fixed at a rapid value that excludes chemical reaction. (b) Reactive strength, in which indentation load is fixed and stressing rate, and thus extent of chemical reaction with the environment, is varied.

Figure 4 highlights the advantages of the controlled flaw indentation strength technique. By controlling the size of the dominant flaw in a specimen, the stress at failure can be varied over a wide range, leading to a wide variation in the consequent fragmentation pattern. Without this control the strengths and resulting patterns would only vary within the limits set by the intrinsic flaw distribution. **Figure 5** shows a sequence of fragmentation patterns that developed in the glass-ceramic discs on failure at the range of strengths shown in Fig. 4. The strengths are indicated above the images. At small strengths the specimens broke into two or three fragments and as the strength increased the number of fragments increased. The fragments are wedge-shaped, formed by cracks radiating from the central flaw. Fig. 1(a) appears as the end member of the sequence. Fragmentation patterns and sequences were similar for the other polycrystalline materials examined here and similar sequences also appear in many of the works regarding fragmentation patterns cited above, most notably the work considering polycrystalline Si [Cook, 2006]. No correlation was observed here between the form of the fragmentation pattern and the method of strength control (indentation flaw size in inert tests or applied stressing rate in reactive tests). Strength appeared to be the sole determiner of the number and shape of fragments, consistent with the works cited above, most notably those in which indentation load and environment [Shetty *et al.*, 1983a] and stressing rate [Salem, 2013] were varied in a similar manner to here. At fixed strength, surface stress increased the number of fragments relative to the base material, also consistent with earlier observations [Shetty *et al.*, 1983a].

Figure 5. Sequence of images of glass-ceramic discs fragmented in biaxial flexure at the strengths indicated. The number of fragments increases with strength and with surface compression (final three discs with strengths > 275 MPa) contained surface compression and central tension.

Observations such as Fig. 5 are placed on a quantitative basis in Fig. 6, which plots the number of fragments observed in strength tests of the six polycrystalline materials examined here. All discs were analyzed by optical microscopy to determine the number of fragments and only those fragments that had become physically separated from their neighbors were counted. In some cases it was clear that cracks had initiated within fragments but had failed to propagate to the edges of the disc. These cracks were not included in computing the number of fragments.

Figure 6. Plots of the number of fragments vs the strength for discs of six polycrystalline materials fractured in biaxial flexure. Symbols represent between 100 and 200 observations of single discs for each material.

There are a number of clear features in Fig. 6: The first feature is a definite trend of more fragments generated by specimens with greater strengths. The second feature is that such a trend is extremely material dependent and individual material variations exhibit significant dispersion (*e.g.*, large strength range with small change in fragment number for the Al₂O₃ materials and the opposite for the glass ceramic). Although the indentation load domain was invariant, the range of strengths generated differed considerably from material to material, indicating a third feature of significant microstructural and hence fracture resistance effects on strength. Microstructural effects include: (i) the strength range covered by the AlN and Cr Al₂O₃ materials is similar yet more fragments were generated in AlN; (ii) the Y₂O₃ material containing hexagonal phase generated more fragments at the same strength than that consisting of cubic phase alone; and (iii) the glass-ceramic material containing a compressive surface stress generated more fragments at the same strength than the base material.

Figure 7 shows a composite logarithmic plot of the responses of the polycrystalline materials in Fig. 6 along with responses for similarly-sized specimens of other materials, including soda-lime silicate glasses (b) [Quinn *et al.*, 2005] and (d) [Nakasa and Nakastuka, 1990], borosilicate glasses (c) [DeLellis *et al.*, 2020] and (e) [Nakasa and Nakastuka, 1990], polycrystalline MgF₂ (a) [Mecholsky *et al.*, 1998], single crystal (f) and polycrystalline (h) Si [Cook, 2006], polycrystalline spinel MgAl₂O₄ (g) [Salem, 2013], polycrystalline partially stabilized ZrO₂ (o) [Nakasa and Nakastuka, 1990], and polycrystalline Al₂O₃ (p) [Nakasa and Nakastuka, 1990]. The responses were determined from published numerical, graphical, or pictorial data from the cited sources. In most cases, the raw data in Fig. 7 were smoothed using a multi-point moving average to remove the dispersion obvious in Fig. 6. The bold solid lines in Fig. 7 are guides to the eye illustrating empirical power law responses of $\sigma^{1.5}$ and $\sigma^{0.5}$.

It is clear that the responses in Fig. 7 fall into two groups dominated by amorphous glasses or crystalline ceramics and semiconductors. The solid line guides to the eye are approximate descriptions of the two groups. The diverse responses are in accord with common experience: a dropped drinking glass usually shatters into many pieces and is largely irrecoverable. A dropped ceramic coffee cup frequently breaks cleanly into a few pieces and is often repairable (“glue the handle back on”) or even transformed into the art of Kintsugi [Richman-Abdou, 2019]. On closer examination and comparison with Table 1, it is clear that there is a tendency to generate more fragments as the Young's modulus E decreases, consistent with the idea that the fragmentation process is the conversion of strain energy into surface energy: greater strain energy generates more fragments. Of course, this is only the driving force element of the thermodynamic balance and does not consider how that conversion is to take place, *i.e.*, whether the fragmentation or branching criterion is met, or if the conversion is possible, as greater fracture resistance R requires greater strain energy to balance the new surfaces created during fragmentation of

tougher, more fracture resistant materials. For instance, the alumina materials may exhibit few fragments because the strain energy at failure is small, the criterion for branching is not met, or the fracture resistance is great. The exceptions to the groups in Fig. 7 highlight the sensitivity of fragmentation to materials details: polycrystalline MgF_2 is grouped with glasses although exhibiting a greater modulus and Si has similar toughness to glass and is grouped with ceramics.

Figure 7. Composite plot of number of fragments formed vs strength for fracture of biaxially flexed discs of glass, ceramics, and semiconductor materials. SLG: soda-lime silicate glass. BSG: borosilicate glass. GC: cordierite glass ceramic. All materials polycrystalline except (b, c, d, e) glasses and (f) single crystal.

Table 1. Polycrystalline ceramic properties and test specimen and rig dimensions

Material	Grain Size d (μm)	Young's Modulus E (GPa)	Fracture Resistance R (J m^{-2})	Specimen Dimensions ($\text{mm} \times \text{mm}$)	Rig Dimensions ($\text{mm} \times \text{mm}$)
Cordierite GC	3	128	18	32×3.3	28×4
Y_2O_3	48	180	8	20×2	18×1.5
MgO	10–26	305	8	32×3.5	28×4
AlN	10	340	12	25×2	20×3.5
Ca- Al_2O_3	15–60	400	20–100	25×1.1	20×2
Cr- Al_2O_3	15–25	400	20–100	27×2	20×2

3. Distribution of fragment sizes

The images of Fig. 5 show that fragments sizes are not identical within a fractured specimen, *i.e.*, there is a distribution of fragment masses. Such size or mass distributions have been considered since early fragmentation studies concerned with exploding armaments [Mott, 1947] and are well reviewed by Grady and Kipp [1985] and Grady [2010], including descriptions of more recent fragmentation distributions generated by controlled blasts and impacts. The original (and still current [Gold and Baker, 2008; Pike and Zuo, 2014]) interest in distributions of fragment masses was directed towards estimating the probability of generating a large fragment able to cause maximal damage in an armament detonation. However, there are many additional areas of application, including rock fragmentation in mining [Hogan *et al.*, 2012, 2014], designing safe structures in architectural and transportation applications [Bennison *et al.*, 1999], ceramic armor (to protect against the large fragments or penetrators) [O'Donnell, 1991; Woodward *et al.*, 1994], forensic evidence investigations [Locke and Unikowski, 1991, 1992; Hicks *et al.*, 1996;], and environmental and geological assessments [Matthews, 1983; Novák-Szabó *et al.*, 2018; Pioli *et al.*, 2019]. Fragment mass distributions also provide fundamental information regarding different mechanisms and material dependencies of the fragmentation process [Åström, 2006]. Here, the distributions of fragment masses resulting from the above glass-ceramic strength tests were determined and compared with distributions resulting from the more frequently reported, predominantly impact, tests.

Glass ceramic specimens with identical numbers of fragments between 2 and 12 were grouped together, independent of strength, and an electric balance used to determine the individual fragment masses, m , constituting a group. Each group consisted of $N = 40\text{--}100$ fragments. As the mass of an intact specimen was approximately 6 g, the number average mass within a group was (6 g/number of fragments). An empirical distribution function (edf), $Pr(m)$, was formed from the fragment masses within each group. The masses were ranked from smallest to largest as $m(i)$ with rank index i varying from 1 to N . The quantity $(i - 0.5)/N$ was generated for each value of the index and the discrete function pairing $Pr(m) = [m(i), (i - 0.5)/N]$ formed the edf for each group. Again, only those fragments that were physically distinct were counted in determining the fragment mass distributions. The function $Pr(m)$ gives the probability that a fragment selected at random from a group has mass $< m$. Figure 8 shows plots of the edf mass variations for each group of glass ceramic fragments for (a) blank, 2–8 fragments, and (b) surface stressed, 9–12 fragments. For ease of visualization, individual fragment masses are shown as symbols for the 2 fragment group and as solid lines for the other groups. The distributions are weakly sigmoidal and move to smaller masses as the number of fragments increases. There was a tendency in some groups of the blank material towards a bimodal

distribution of large and small fragments. This was particularly evident in the edf of the 6 fragment group but also in the distributions of the 4, 5, and 7 fragment groups. Visual support for the observation is clear in Fig. 5 and no doubt reflects the inhomogeneity of the flat on three-balls test geometry [Börger *et al.*, 2002, 2004]. For historical reasons associated with estimating the probability of forming large, destructive, exploding shell fragments, fragment mass distribution data are usually presented as the complementary edf, $\overline{Pr}(m) = 1 - Pr(m)$ [Grady and Kipp, 1985, Grady, 2010]. The data in Fig. 8 would then decrease with increasing mass as $\overline{Pr}(m)$ gives the probability that a fragment selected at random from a group has mass $> m$. Greater insight into the relative forms of the distributions in Fig. 8 is gained however by scaling the mass axes to common values.

Figure 8. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of fragment mass for glass ceramic disc specimens fractured in biaxial flexure and exhibiting the different numbers of fragments indicated. (a) Blank specimens. (b) Stressed specimens containing surface compression and central tension. Stressed specimens exhibit greater numbers of fragments and different shaped edf responses.

Figure 9(a) is a composite distribution plot with the fragment mass domain in each distribution scaled by the specific distribution median mass, $M = m/m_{\text{median}}$. Identical notation to Fig. 8 is used and all distributions in the scaled coordinates pass through (1, 0.5). It is clear that the relative width of the distributions, dispersion in M , increases as the number of fragments increases (from 2 to 8), *i.e.*, the relative separation between the lightest and heaviest fragments increases as the number of fragments and, see Fig. 7, the strength increases. An alternative interpretation is thus that the fragmentation process becomes more disordered as the strength increases. Figure 9(a) also shows that this disorder is suppressed by a compressive surface stress. Although the strengths and numbers of fragments are large for the surface-stressed (S) materials, the variability in M is less than the trend strength would suggest.

Figure 9. Plots of fragment mass distributions from Fig. 8 using scaled mass axes. (a) Distributions scaled by median mass illustrating increased relative mass dispersion with greater number of fragments. (b) Distributions scaled by mass domain width illustrating near-linear distributions.

Figure 9(b) is a composite distribution plot with fragment masses scaled by relative position in a distribution mass domain, $\mu = (m - m_{\min}) / (m_{\max} - m_{\min})$. In this case, all distributions in the scaled coordinates pass through (0, 0) and (1, 1). The similarities in edf shapes within the blank and surface stressed material groups are clear—the blank materials exhibit weakly perturbed linear variations and the surface stressed materials exhibit concave variations. The nature of the blank material edf perturbation, from linear to bimodal, noted above, is observed in the many horizontal segments. The small-mass branches of the bimodal responses appear to be in common and overlie the surface stressed responses, suggesting that fragment mass disorder is suppressed at large strengths, generating a common edf.

The behavior of the cordierite glass ceramic is most easily compared with that of other fragmentation systems using a plotting scheme similar to Fig. 9(a). Such a comparison is shown in Fig. 10: Fragment mass edf plots for several “typical” fragmentation systems were determined by digitizing published works and scaling to a common format. The mass axes were scaled to distribution median values as M . The edf axes were scaled to distribution maxima as 1.0. The resulting symbols in Fig. 10 indicate digitized values for: (a) an impacted thin SiO₂ plate sandwiched between polymer layers [Grady and Kipp, 1985]; (b) an impacted granite block [Hogan *et al.*, 2012]; (c) a dropped clay tablet [Meibom and Balsev, 1996]; (d) an impacted ZrO₂ cylinder [Davydova *et al.*, 2018]; and (e) an impacted egg shell (predominantly CaCO₃) [Wittel *et al.*, 2004]. The cordierite glass ceramic flexed discs appear as (f). The great extent of the relative fragment mass domains in systems (a)–(e) necessitated the use of a logarithmic scale, which also enables direct comparison of edf shapes independent of fragment mass magnitude. All plots in Fig. 10 extend over 10⁶ in M .

The most obvious feature of Fig. 10 is the commonality of the relative fragment mass domains observed in the typical fragmentation experiments (a)–(e), about 10⁴. These domains are quite different from the extent of the disc fragmentation system (f), about 10¹. Flexure generated fragments clearly exhibit distribution widths different from typical impact generated fragments. A second clear feature of Fig. 10 is that there is no common distribution shape. Although the shapes differ considerably, most typical fragmentation systems exhibit a convex tendency, which is distinct from the near-linear tendency of the disc fragmentation system, Fig. 9(b).

Figure 10. Plots of experimental edf behavior for five typical fragmentation systems and the glass-ceramic disc data. (a)–(e) Symbols represents experimental data, lines represent empirical best fits. (f) Lines represent experimental data from Figs. 8 and 9.

In more detail, the solid lines in Fig. 10(a)–(e) represent best fits to the data using equations frequently implemented to describe fragmentation distributions. In accord with the usual plotting scheme, the equations are usually given as complementary cumulative distribution functions, $\bar{H}(m)$, fit to $\overline{Pr}(m)$ data. Here, cumulative distribution functions $H(M) = 1 - \bar{H}(M)$, in scaled coordinate M , are fit to $Pr(M)$ data. In Fig. 10(a), $\bar{H} = A \exp(-M^{1/2})$, now known as the Mott distribution [Grady and Kipp, 1985], is used, where A is fitting parameter. This behavior is

exhibited by cylindrical steel shells [Weimer and Rogers, 1979]. A more flexible equation, $\bar{H} = A \exp(-M^\alpha)$, the stretched exponential, is illustrated in Fig. 10(b), where A and α are fitting parameters. Such an equation describes most sigmoidal appearing data; $\alpha = 1$, the exponential distribution, describes fragmented expanded rings [Grady and Kipp, 1985]. Of even greater flexibility is the bilinear exponential equation, $\bar{H} = A \exp(-M^\alpha) + B \exp(-M^\beta)$, illustrated in Fig. 10(c), where A , α , B , and β are fitting parameters. Such an equation describes many explosion generated fragment distributions [Grady and Kipp, 1985]. A final equation is the simple power law $\bar{H} = A M^{-\alpha}$, illustrated in Figs. 10(d) and (e), where A and α are fitting parameters. This equation has been used extensively and examples include impact fragments of glass and ferroelectric spheres [Gilvarry and Bergstrom, 1961; Grady, 2008]; gypsum discs and spheres [Oddershedde *et al.*, 1993], Si plates [Huang *et al.*, 2016], a large variety of glass and ceramic plates and rods, including Al_2O_3 , SiC, ZrO_2 , and granite [O'Donnell, 1991; Woodward *et al.*, 1994; Davydova *et al.*, 2013, 2015, 2017, 2018; Zinszer *et al.*, 2015], and meteoric fragments [Halliday *et al.*, 1989]. In contrast, the disc data are described by a simple linear relationship $\bar{H} = 0.5 + A(1 - M)$, where A is a fitting parameter, Fig. 9. It is to be recognized that these equations are empirical descriptions. An extensive survey of over 1000 fragmentation data sets and 17 distributions [Sanchidrián *et al.*, 2014] concluded that “No general quantitative indications can be given on what characteristics a data set must have to be best fitted by one or another distribution.”

4. Crack branching distances

The number and size distribution of the fragments generated on specimen fracture depends on the distance between crack branching events and the angles between crack branches. The major factor is the crack branching distance and branching angles will not be considered here. However, it is noted that the angles observed in the ceramics studied in this work and elsewhere were typically about 45° , although variation was considerable; both factors recognized in early work [Preston, 1935]. The value is less than that determined for distortion of the crack tip stress field during dynamic fracture. As first calculated by Yoffe [1951], crack velocities are large during dynamic fracture and the maximum crack tip tensile stress does not occur directly ahead of the tip but in two lobes at approximately $\pm 60^\circ$ to the crack plane. A recent review of crack branching angle observations in specimens of various geometries suggests that the angle and its variation is a sensitive function of the shear/tension mode of loading [Quinn, 2020]. Here the loading will be primarily restricted to equibiaxial tension in loaded discs.

Figure 11 is a schematic diagram of the branching phenomenon observed in failure of a disc containing a strength controlling indentation flaw, similar to Fig. 2. Branching occurs at radii r_i measured from the flaw center and the “branching distance” is taken as the average of the two initial radii, $\lambda_b = (r_1 + r_2)/2$. These radii are typically the shortest in a branching pattern and frequently indistinguishable.

Figure 11. Schematic diagram of crack branching at fracture from an indentation flaw. The central impression of the indentation is visible along with two cracks propagating left and right leading to branching and fragmentation. The branching radii r_i and principle branching distance λ_b are illustrated.

Figure 12 shows a logarithmic plot of the variation in λ_b with σ_f for the blank glass-ceramic disc specimens shown in Figs. 4, 6, and 8. Individual symbols represent measurements from single specimens. The branching distances of order millimeters for strengths of hundreds of megapascals are typical for ceramics and glasses. Also typical is that the branching distance decreased significantly with increased strength. The solid line in Fig. 12 is a best fit to the data of a commonly observed and reported description (see below) for branching of $\lambda_b = S\sigma_f^{-2}$, where S is an empirical “branching constant”. The data in Fig. 12 are well described by this equation over the domain of strengths measured.

Figure 12. Plot of branching distance vs strength for cordierite glass ceramic discs. The symbols represent individual specimen measurements and the solid line represents an empirical fit to the data of the form $\lambda_b \sim \sigma_f^{-2}$.

Figure 13 shows the results of an extensive survey of branching distances, including the polycrystalline AlN, MgO, and glass ceramic materials examined here along with glasses and other polycrystalline ceramics. The families of materials are labelled for ease of reference and include soda-lime silicate glass (SLG), borosilicate glass (BSG), MgO (M), glass ceramic (GC), SiC (SC), Si₃N₄ (SN), AlN (AN), Al₂O₃ (A), and ZrO₂ (Z). For example, the cordierite glass ceramic material shown in Fig. 12 is labelled GC1. The results from other researchers include those from Congleton and Petch [1965] (SLG1, M1, A2), Aoki and Sakata [1980] (SLG2, BSG1), Shetty *et al.*, [1983a] (SLG3, GC2, A3), Oakley [1996] (SLG4), Quinn [1999] (BSG2), Choi and Gyekenyesi [1998] [SLG5, SC, SN1, SN2, SN3, SN4, Z2), Choi *et al.* [2000] (A1), and Kirchner *et al.* [1981] (Z1).

Figure 13. Plot of branching distance vs strength for a variety of glass and ceramics. The symbols represent individual specimen measurements and the solid lines represent empirical fits to the data of the form $\lambda_b \sim \sigma_f^{-2}$. The shaded region is invariant and a guide to the eye.

The results from other researchers in Fig. 13 were obtained by digitizing published data and scaling to a single format. Some commonly cited results, in which branching distances were inferred from fracture surface features, *e.g.*, [Kirchner, 1978; Kirchner and Kirchner, 1979], are not included. The format of Figs 12 and 13 has the independent failure variable, the strength σ_f , as the abscissa and the dependent variable, the branching distance λ_b , as the ordinate, and uses the same logarithmic scale (1:2) in all cases. The format enables an unbiased assessment of the $\sigma_f\lambda_b$ relationship for a given material and easy between-material comparisons. (A common format reverses the independent and dependent variables and linearizes the data assuming a particular relationship; see many of the works cited above.) Between-material comparisons are further enhanced by the inclusion of an invariant shaded triangular contour along the value $S = 10 \text{ MPa}^2 \text{ m}$ in each sub-plot. Contours of S in the shaded region are < 10 and those in the unshaded region > 10 . The solid lines in Fig. 13 are best fits to the data of the form $\lambda_b = S\sigma_f^{-2}$. The materials, identification labels, number of observations, and the best fit values of S are given in Table 2, along with the data source first author and year. The values given in Table 2 are means and standard deviations of the experimental quantity $\sigma_f^2\lambda_b$ evaluated for each material. The lines and values should be interpreted as representative contours of branching behavior assuming the quadratic form given, rather than unbiased descriptions of the observed behavior. The sub-plots in Fig. 13 are arranged so that materials with smaller values of S are represented in the lower left of the figure and materials with larger values are represented in the upper right.

There are many clear trends apparent in Fig. 13 and Table 2. First, for all materials examined, crack branching distance decreased with increasing strength, independent of the nature of the strength controlling flaw (indentation, machining abrasion, incidental contact), the strength measurement environment (inert, reactive), or the measurement geometry (ball on ring, ring on ring, flat on balls). In some cases, the strength domain was limited by a limited domain of uncontrolled flaws (*e.g.*, A1, M1, Z1) such that a clear trend is difficult to detect, although large numbers of specimens containing uncontrolled flaws can give rise to significant trend (*e.g.*, SLG4). In other cases, controlled indentation flaws were used to extend the flaw size domains with consequent extended strength domains (*e.g.*, SLG3, BSG2, GC1) and clear and significant branching trends were observed. Second, glasses tend to exhibit behavior on contours of $S < 10 \text{ MPa}^2 \text{ m}$ and ceramics on contours of $S > 10 \text{ MPa}^2 \text{ m}$. That is, glass observations (all SLG, BSG) appear within the shaded region and ceramic observations (all others) appear within the unshaded region. Third, in more detail regarding the last point, there is a clear gradation of behavior from optical glasses (*e.g.*, SLG1), through microelectronic glass ceramics and ceramics (*e.g.*, GC1), to structural ceramics (*e.g.*, Z2) in terms of increasing fragmentation resistance as quantified by movement from lower left to upper right in Fig. 13 or top to bottom in Table 2 (MgF₂ now groups with ceramics). Intuitively, greater fragmentation resistance is associated with

greater fracture resistance (and, coincidentally, usually greater elastic modulus and contact hardness). This association extends to within material comparisons: the solid symbols in the Z1A sub plot indicate peak aged material with greater transformation toughening and clearly greater fragmentation resistance; the solid symbols in the GC1S sub plot indicate surface compressed material with somewhat greater fragmentation resistance. An opposite case is the SN1 material tested at 1100 °C with less fragmentation resistance than the other SN materials. Figure 14 is a plot of all the S values determined here, using the same notation as Fig. 13 and ranked in increasing order making the above material dependencies clear.

Figure 14. Plot of material branching constant S ranked by mean value. Glasses have S values $< 10 \text{ MPa}^2 \text{ m}$ (shaded region) and ceramics have S values $> 10 \text{ MPa}^2 \text{ m}$. More fragmentation resistant materials on right of plot. (Note that $10 \text{ MPa}^2 \text{ m} = 10^4 \text{ MPa}^2 \text{ mm}$.)

A final observation from Fig. 13 is that the branching behavior of some materials is not completely described by $\lambda_b = S\sigma_f^{-2}$. The most common deviation is that the response has a stronger dependence on strength. In cases in which the deviation is small the empirical relation can be modified to describe the observed behavior as $\lambda_b = S(\sigma_f - \sigma_0)^{-2}$, where σ_0 is an empirical shift parameter, *e.g.*, SLG4, BSG2. In cases in which the deviation is large the empirical power-law relation $\lambda_b = S\sigma_f^{-x}$ is required, where $x > 2$ is an empirical exponent, *e.g.*, SLG5, GC2, A3. These factors should be taken into account when interpreting Fig. 14.

Table 2. Crack branching parameters of glasses and ceramics

Data Source	Material	S (MPa ² m)	N (Observations)	Identification
Congleton, 1965	Soda lime glass	2.48 ± 0.76	17	SLG1
Aoki, 1980	Soda lime glass	3.35 ± 1.16	17	SLG2
Aoki, 1980	Borosilicate glass	3.98 ± 0.54	17	BSG1
Shetty, 1983	Soda lime glass	5.34 ± 0.30	14	SLG3
Oakley, 1996	Soda lime glass	5.66 ± 0.85	540	SLG4
Quinn, 1999	Borosilicate glass	6.75 ± 1.14	46	BSG2
Choi, 1998	Soda lime glass	13.0 ± 4.8	43	SLG5
Congleton, 1965	MgO	18.8 ± 4.2	10	M1
This work	Cordierite	21.2 ± 9.2	59	GC1
Shetty, 1983	Cordierite	23.4 ± 7.5	37	GC2
Mecholsky, 1998	MgF ₂	24.5 ± 3	2	
This work	MgO	27.4 ± 11.2	15	M2
Choi, 1998	SiC	29.4 ± 3.6	34	SC
This work	Cordierite	31.7 ± 12.7	21	GC1S
Choi, 1998	Si ₃ N ₄	34.3 ± 16.9	20	SN1
This work	AlN	36.7 ± 10.8	14	AN
Choi, 2000	Al ₂ O ₃	54.6 ± 8.7	25	A1
Congleton, 1965	Al ₂ O ₃	56.4 ± 13.0	22	A2
Choi, 1998	Si ₃ N ₄	74.1 ± 43.4	12	SN2
Shetty, 1983	Al ₂ O ₃	90.1 ± 38.8	41	A3
Kirchner, 1981	ZrO ₂	91.1 ± 28.5	9	Z1
Choi, 1998	Si ₃ N ₄	122.2 ± 34.3	12	SN3
Choi, 1998	Si ₃ N ₄	124.1 ± 59.0	20	SN4
Choi, 1998	ZrO ₂	143.9 ± 30.8	14	Z2
Kirchner, 1981	ZrO ₂	465 ± 116	10	Z1A

5. Application Examples

In this section, three sets of results are presented, without analysis, as examples of potential applications of the work above. Two of the examples concern the number of fragments generated during component failure—Si die fragmentation and ceramic microstructure effects on fragmentation—and one example concerns crack branching—the variation of branching radii in a fragmentation sequence. The first two examples are applicable in component and materials engineering and the third example is applicable in developing a fundamental basis for fragmentation.

5.1. Si die failure

Figure 15 shows an array of rectangular single crystal Si dies used in microelectronic devices. The dies are approximately 15 mm × 10 mm and are mounted active face down with a polymeric adhesive to a composite polymer-glass fiber substrate such that the inactive (001) die face is visible. The die edges are aligned along [110] directions. The die active faces, substrates, and adhesive layers are not visible. The dies and substrates are approximately 0.7 mm and 1 mm thick, respectively. The entire die-substrate assembly was cooled to approximately $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then warmed to room temperature. The greater coefficient of thermal expansion of the substrates relative to the Si dies caused bending of the assemblies on cooling, placing the back faces of the dies in biaxial tension. The images of Fig. 15 were recorded after the cooling cycle and warming the assemblies to room temperature.

The dies have fragmented along [110] directions as a consequence of the cooling cycle, similar to [100] branching observed in MgO [Bowden *et al.*, 1967]. The number of fragments for each die in Fig. 15 is indicated; the number of fragments increasing from top to bottom. The bottom right image in Fig. 15 is a schematic diagram generated by close examination of the most fragmented die, illustrating the 27 fragments. The practical application of Fig. 15 is in establishing the strength distribution of dies and propensity to failure in an assembly. The stress developed in a die is determinable from substrate, adhesive, and die thermomechanical properties, assembly geometry, and cooling temperature. The strength of a die is determinable from fragmentation data such as Figs 6. and 7. Comparison of the stress and strength enables model verification and engineering of die edge finishing and strength-controlling flaws, adhesive fixing temperature, and substrate materials and geometry. Even in the absence of calculation, comparison of Figs. 7 and 15 enables the peak stress reached by the dies during the cooling cycle to be estimated as 500 MPa. The advantage of fragmentation data in engineering trouble shooting is clear as they address the question of “over-stressed or under-strength?”

Figure 15. Sequence of optical images of Si dies fragmented in biaxial flexure generated by thermal expansion mismatch with an underlying polymeric substrate (not visible) The number of fragments is indicated, along with a schematic diagram of the most fragmented die.

5.2. Ceramic microstructure development

Figure 16 shows the variation of fragmentation tendency as a ceramic microstructure develops and, in particular, how the number of fragments varies with strength as controlled by relative density or porosity. The upper sub plot of Fig. 16 shows the number of fragments formed as a function of strength for Al_2O_3 from the work of Sapozhnikov *et al.* [2015]. The relative density of fired Al_2O_3 discs was varied by controlling the pressure used to form the discs in the green state, thereby altering the fired relative density from 0.77 to 0.96 with consequent increase in strength. The number of fragments increased with increasing strength (and density) towards the representative response of dense ceramics reproduced from Fig. 7 as the solid line.

Figure 16. Plots of number of fragments as a function of strength for two ceramics of varying relative density, (upper) Al_2O_3 and (lower) cordierite glass ceramic. As density increases, strength and the number of fragments generated on failure increase.

The lower sub plot in Fig. 16 shows the number of fragments formed as a function of strength for cordierite glass ceramic. The relative density of fired glass ceramic discs was varied by controlling the volume fraction of Si₃N₄ whiskers added to the discs in the green state from 0.15 to 0, thereby altering the fired relative density from 0.85 to 0.99 with consequent increase in strength. As above, the number of fragments increased with increasing strength (and density) towards the representative response of dense ceramics. The sensitivity of the number of fragments to strength is significant for both materials in Fig. 16 and reinforces the observations of Fig. 7. However, the interpretation is somewhat different. In Fig. 7, variations in strength and the number of fragments were caused by variations in the size of strength controlling flaws for a given material. In Fig. 16, variations in strength are caused by variations in flaw size (probably pore size) *and* variations in material (different density and microstructure). The practical application of Fig. 16 is in designing and engineering ceramic fabrication methods and microstructures with optimized fragmentation behavior and in reducing diagnosis of fabrication state to a semi-quantitative measurement (number of fragments, not strength).

5.3. Branching radius variation

The number and mass distribution of fragments generated on failure of a brittle component depends on the detailed variations of the branching geometry (angle, radii) with branching node. In particular, a major factor is the variation of branching radius, r_i , with node index i , Fig. 11. The early schematic diagrams of Preston [1935] make clear that a non-linear increase in r_i with i was observed in uniaxial and biaxial loading of glass plates and pressure loading of bottles. Somewhat later images of uniaxial failure of glass plates by Clark and Irwin [1966], Bowden *et al.* [1967], and Field [1971] indicate similar non-linear behavior (and also, in agreement with Preston, very small, $\sim 20^\circ$, uniaxial branching angles). Figure 17 places the branching radius behavior on a quantitative basis in plots of r_i vs i for glasses and ceramics. The upper plot in Fig. 17 shows data, digitized from published images of glass uniaxial fracture, from (a) Clark and Irwin [1966] and (b) Bowden *et al.* [1967] and Field [1971]. Individual symbols represent measurements at individual branching nodes. Comparison of different systems is enabled by normalizing the branching radii as r_i/r_1 , noting that for these unidirectional fragmentation patterns $r_1 = \lambda_b$ and r_2 is distinct from r_1 . A clear feature is that the branching radii at a given node exhibit considerable dispersion such that there is considerable overlap between radii at adjacent nodes. (An alternative interpretation is that the radii are quantized and that the nodes exhibit dispersion.) The shaded band highlights the non-linear variation of radius with node and is of the form $(r_i/r_1 - 1) \sim (i - 1)^2$, clearly describing the median behavior and ranges of radii.

Figure 17. Plots of branching node radii for uniaxial and biaxial loading and fragmentation of glasses and ceramics. Symbols represent measurements of (normalized) radii at the crack branching nodes indicated. The shaded bands are guides to the eye of quadratic variation.

The lower plot in Fig. 17 shows data from glass and ceramic biaxial fracture, digitized from published sources where necessary, for (a) soda-lime silicate glass [Terao, 1978], (b) ZrO_2 [Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1990], (c) AlN (AN, this work), (d) (350 ± 35) MPa strength cordierite glass ceramic (GC1, this work), (e) (245 ± 25) MPa GC1, (g) (140 ± 25) MPa GC1, (f) BSG [Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1990], (h) (245 ± 25) MPa surface stressed GC1S, and (i) laminated and thermally tempered glass [Sakai *et al.*, 1991]. As above, individual symbols represent

measurements at individual branching nodes. Symbols with lines represent measurements at branching nodes averaged over many specimens; the lines are guides to the eye. The same normalization and scale is used as in the upper plot, noting that for these multidirectional fragmentation patterns $r_1 + r_2 = 2\lambda_b$ and $r_2 \simeq r_1$. Once again, there is considerable overlap between radii at adjacent nodes and the shaded band highlights the non-linear variation of radius with node of the form $(r_i/r_1 - 1) \sim (i - 1)^2$, although with smaller amplitude than the upper plot. Systems (h) and (i) are regarded as toughened and yet are not clearly distinguished from the other biaxial systems, and no significant distinction between the strength levels of the GC1 system, (d)–(f), is observed.

Overall, Fig. 17 demonstrates the quadratic “stretching out” during fragmentation pattern development, the dispersion in node radii (or vice versa), the difference in uniaxial and biaxial patterns, and the weak material dependence of normalized pattern shape. These features form the fundamental basis for fragmentation model development as demonstrated, for example, by probabilistic sequential algorithms [Quinn *et al.*, 2005] or described by fractal like dimensions [Nakasa and Nakatsuka, 1994; Mecholsky *et al.*, 1998].

6. Conclusions

An extensive examination of experimental data, both new and previously published, describing fracture of biaxially stressed brittle discs has placed many fragmentation phenomena on a firm quantitative basis. Data, many requiring new digitization from published sources, from over forty materials fragmentation systems and hundreds of specimens, were examined. The phenomena have been characterized at three length scales—(i) that of the discs, the number of fragments, (ii) that of the fragments, the distribution of fragment masses, and (iii) that of the propagating fracture, the variation of crack branching distances. For the first phenomenon, a distinction between ceramics and glasses is observed. Ceramic failures generate fewer fragments at the same failure strength than glasses and the number of fragments generated have a weaker dependence on strength. No dependence on the number of fragments with flaw type, specimen environment, or testing protocol is observed. Failure of ceramic and glass discs containing small specimen-level stresses generates far fewer fragments, tens at most, than chemically stressed or physically tempered glass specimens, which typically number hundreds, suggesting different fracture mechanics bases. For the second phenomenon, a clear distinction exists between disc fragment mass distributions and impact or explosion fragment mass distributions. Although the dispersion of disc fragment mass distributions increases with strength, the relative domain width, about a factor of 10, is very small compared with impact or explosion generated fragment mass distributions, about a factor of 10^4 , suggesting a different probabilistic basis. For the third phenomenon, no dependence of crack branching distance on flaw type, specimen environment, or testing protocol is observed. To first order, an inverse quadratic dependence of crack branching distance on strength is observed, and the resulting branching coefficient can be used to rank the fragmentation resistance of materials. For all three phenomena, the indentation-strength method provides a great advantage in expanding and determining the domains of flaws and thus strengths responsible for the strain energies in specimens at failure and thus range of fragmentation behavior. The data here provide a quantitative basis for simulation of fundamental fragmentation phenomena and qualitative examples of applications in materials and component development.

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